

Enhancing Soil Health, Crop Productivity and Financial Viability Through INM Approaches in Cowpea¹

Meenakhi Prusty

Department of Soil Science, College of Agriculture, Odisha University of Agriculture & Technology,
Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

Nityamanjari Mishra

Department of Vegetable Science, College of Agriculture, Odisha University of Agriculture &
Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

Gyanranjan Sahoo

Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Odisha University of Agriculture & Technology, Nayagarh, Odisha

Sunil Samal

Department of Fruit Science, College of Agriculture, Odisha University of Agriculture & Technology,
Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

Monika Ray

Regional Research and Technology Transfer Station, Odisha University of Agriculture & Technology,
Keonjhar, Odisha, India

Md Abdul Alim

AICRP on Weed Management, Odisha University of Agriculture & Technology,
Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

Sasmita Behera

Department of Fruit Science, College of Agriculture, Odisha University of Agriculture & Technology,
Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

Abstract

The study entitled “Enhancing soil health, crop productivity and financial viability through INM approaches in cowpea” was conducted at RRTTS, Mahisapat, Dhenkanal, during kharif season of 2020 and 2021, with eight different INM practices which included (T₁) Absolute control, (T₂) Farmers practice, (T₃) Soil test dose(STD), (T₄) STD₁₀₀+R+PSM, (T₅) STD₇₅+R+PSM+FYM, (T₆) STD₁₀₀+R+PSM+FYM, (T₇) STD₇₅+R+PSM+VC, (T₈) STD₁₀₀+R+PSM+VC. The integrated application of biofertilizers *Rhizobium* (R) at 20 g/kg of seed and PSM at 4 kg/ha, FYM at 5 t/ha or vermicompost (VC) at 2.5 t/ha, and lime at 0.2 LR as per the treatment imposed in the experiment. Among all treatments T₇ exhibited best results in characters like plant height (54.3 cm), root length (30.8 cm), no. of

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nodules per plant (41), pod length (33.2 cm) and no. of pods per plant (17). Highest yield was observed with integration of STD₇₅ along with BFs and VC; 5.32 and 8.45 t ha⁻¹ following different package of practices. The highest uptake of macro nutrients in pod (128.6, 23.2 and 14.4 kg ha⁻¹, respectively) and in stover (33.2, 22.2, 24.8 kg ha⁻¹, respectively) was observed in T₈. The highest microbial population of 49.40 (x 10⁶cfu g⁻¹ of soil), 22.63 (x 10⁵cfu g⁻¹ of soil) and 30.93 (x 10⁴cfu g⁻¹ of soil) were recorded in T₈ followed by T₇. Such a practice package was judged to be advantageous because it generated the highest net return of Rs 1, 51,400, resulting in the highest B:C ratio of 3.80.

Keywords

Cowpea, Economics, INM, Microbial activity, Phosphate Solubilizing Mycorrhizae.

Introduction

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L.) is a significant vegetable produce that is a part of Fabaceae family, with a chromosome number of 2n=22. It originated in Central Africa and is known for its deep root system, ability for biological nitrogen fixation, Undissolved soil nutrient extraction and positive impact on soil quality. Vegetable cowpea is cultivated for its green pods, as fodder, or for green manure purposes. It boasts a protein content of 24.8%, carbohydrate content of 63.6%, and fat content of 1.9%, providing it with a wealth of vital vitamins and minerals, including calcium and iron (Shaw, 2007).

Compared to cereal grains, cowpea seeds are abundant in the amino acids lysine and tryptophan but lack methionine and cystine. The cultivation of cowpeas is becoming increasingly popular among vegetable growers due to their short growth duration, quick maturation, high yield, and profitability per unit area, gradually replacing traditional summer vegetable crops. In India, cowpeas are cultivated on approximately 3.9 million hectares, with a national output of 685 kg ha⁻¹ (Rathore *et al.*, 2015). The primary cowpea-growing states in India include Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Madhya Pradesh, and surrounding regions of Himachal Pradesh.

Integrated Nutrient Management (INM) aims to maintain soil fertility, enhance crop productivity, and promote ecological, social, and economic sustainability. It involves the combined use of organic, inorganic, and biological sources of plant nutrients. The primary objectives of INM are to increase productivity, sustainability, and soil fertility, improve nutrient use efficiency, and preserve soil quality. The integration of organic manures with mineral fertilizers enhances nutrient availability, cation retention, and fertilizer efficiency. This approach ensures a balanced and sustainable agricultural system without compromising soil health. Cowpea is a potential vegetable grown in the Mid-central table land zone of Odisha. Yield of cowpea is not up to the mark due to improper nutrient management in the state. Therefore, INM including both organic and inorganic source of nutrients is expected to enhance the crop yield and also maintain the soil fertility. Given these considerations, the current study, "Effect of INM practices on yield and quality of cowpea in Mid Central Table Land zone

of Odisha," was conducted at the RRTTS, OUAT, Mahisapat, Dhenkanal research farm during Kharif 2020 and 2021.

Material and method

The Regional Research and Technology Transfer Station of the Odisha University of Agriculture and Technology, situated at Mahisapat in the Dhenkanal district in the Mid Central Table Land Zone of Odisha, was the site of an empirical study conducted in 2020 and 2021. Geographically, the farm lies between latitudes 20°-3' and 21°-16' North and longitudes 84° and 86°-6' East. The zone's key soil types are lateritic (Oxisol), black (Vertisol), red-laterite (Alfisol), and alluvial (Entisol). The experimental site's soil was red, sandy loam (containing 79.2% sand, 6.2% silt, and 14.6% clay), acidic in response (pH=5.6), and had medium available K₂O (228 kg ha⁻¹) and low available N (248 kg ha⁻¹) and P₂O₅ (12.0 kg ha⁻¹).

With three replications and eight treatments, the experiment was set up in RBD. Table 1 provides a full breakdown of the procedures.

Cowpea crop (var. Kashi Kanchan) was sown in July with a plant spacing of 30 cm x 10 cm in each experimental plot. The crop received a combination of N-P₂O₅-K₂O fertilizers in the form of urea, navaratna, and MOP. Additionally, FYM, vermicompost, and biofertilizers like Rhizobium and PSM were applied as per treatment. Fertilizers were applied in two splits, while organics and biofertilizers were used as a basal application. Lime was applied using paper mill sludge in all treatments except the control. Using nutritional agar as a growth medium and serial dilution, the pour plate method was used to count the bacterial colonies, as explained by S. A. Waksman (1927). According to Ryckeboer et al. (2003), the fungal colony count was performed using the pour plate method after serial dilution, using rose-bengal chloramphenicol agar as the growth medium. Using actinomycetes agar as a growth medium, the actinomycetes colony count was performed using the pour plate method after serial dilution, as outlined by Williams and Davies (1963).

After full maturity (90-95 days), the crop was cut and pods were collected from representative plots. The cumulative yield was recorded as final yield. Five plants were chosen at random from each plot, uprooted from the ground, and a dry sample of the plant and pods was taken from each treatment. The local market prices were used as the basis for calculating the economics of farming. The recorded data was statistically evaluated using Randomized Block Design (RBD), in accordance with the methods described by Gomez and Gomez (1984).

Result and Discussion:

Effect of INM practices on growth parameters of Cowpea crop

The data related to the growth parameters of the cowpea crop under the influence of INM practices have been presented in Fig.1. Plant height under the influence of different treatments varied significantly between 37.2 cm to 54.3 cm, shortest with control and tallest with the integrated treatment comprising of STD₇₅ + seed treatment with *Rhizobium* @ 20g/kg of seed + PSM @ 4kg/ha (BFs) + VC applied @ 2.5 t/ha. Suboptimal dose of STD (STD₇₅) when integrated with BFs + F / BFs + VC significantly increased the crop growth over FP, STD alone and STD₁₀₀ + BFs practices and at

par with $STD_{100} + BF_s + F$. However, use of VC had greater influence on crop growth compared to the use of FYM (F) (7.9%) when integrated with STD_{75} . The root length under the influence of different INM treatments varied significantly between 18.1 cm to 30.8 cm and Integration of suboptimal dose of STD (STD_{75}) with BF_s and VC influenced the root length to the highest extent with an increase of 38.1 per cent over lone STD. The pod length varied significantly between 18.8cm and 33.2cm, lowest with control and highest with integration of suboptimal dose (STD_{75}) with BF_s and VC. Integration of STD_{75} with BF_s and VC influenced the pod length highest with an increase of 43.1 per cent over lone STD. The integrated use of BF_s (R+PSM) and STD_{100} increased the number of pods by 10 per cent to lone STD (STD_{75}) when integrated with BF_s and VC influenced the pod number per plant the highest (70%). The rhizosphere is a vibrant ecosystem full of microbes that play a key role in root and plant activity. Rhizobium and PSM are beneficial microbes that help with root nodule formation and can be used as microbial inoculants for nitrogen and phosphorus availability (Pattanaik *et al.*, 2016). These microbes work well together and are particularly important for improving growth in cowpea crops. By combining organic matter and biofertilizers with traditional fertilizers, a favourable environment for crop growth can be achieved. Similar was found by Dwivedi *et al.* (2022).

Effect of INM practices on Yield of Cowpea crop

Different practices of integrated nutrient management (INM) had a significant impact on pod yield, with a range of 7.28 to 10.27 t ha⁻¹. The best results were seen with the integration of suboptimal dose (STD_{75}) with bio-fertilizers (BF_s) and vermicompost (VC), which led to a 41.0% increase in pod yield compared to the control. Economic yield also improved with the use of fertilizers, organics, and bio-fertilizers, either alone or in combination. Total biomass production varied from 5.32 to 8.76 t ha⁻¹, with the highest yield seen in the treatment combining STD_{75} , BF_s, and VC as given in table 2. This practice was found to be superior to using STD alone, and was comparable to using STD_{100} with BF_s and VC, resulting in a 25% cost savings on organic fertilizers. It was due to more readily bioavailable nutrients in vermicompost in comparison to FYM and more microbial load over vermicompost which helps in nutrient mineralization (Patra *et al.*, 2022).

The study showed that the harvest index of cowpea crops varied depending on different integrated nutrient management practices. The highest harvest index was observed with the integration of suboptimal dose with biofertilizers and vermicompost, while the lowest was with the control practice. The economic yield justified the significance of integrated input use, with the $STD_{75}+BF_s+VC$ practice resulting in the highest performance (141%). The relative agronomic efficiency based on biomass yield was also highest with the same practice. This was likely due to increased availability of essential nutrients, which promoted early root growth and improved nutrient absorption from deeper soil layers, leading to increased growth, biomass production, harvest index, and agronomic efficiency. The present findings have been corroborated by Kumar and Pandita (2014).

Effect of INM practices on nutrient uptake of cow pea

Various agricultural practices were tested for their impact on nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) uptake compared to control practices and presented in Fig. 2. Overall, the use of

fertilizers and organic materials significantly increased N, P, and K uptake compared to control. The N uptake increased by 19.1 per cent due to FP which was statistically at par with the uptake due to lone STD. For P uptake, integrating STD with BFs, FYM, or VC all showed increases in uptake (12.3%) compared to STD alone. For K uptake, the use of fertilizers and organic materials also showed significant increases in uptake, with VC proving to be a superior practice. Overall, integrating different practices for productivity improvement had a positive impact on nutrient uptake in crops. Replacement of FYM use with VC in the practice significantly increased K uptake, hence use of VC proved to be superior practice. Combined use of BFs+F and STD₇₅ was statistically at par with BFs+F and STD₁₀₀. The integrated use of BFs+VC with STD₇₅ showed 10 per cent increase in K uptake when integrated with STD₁₀₀. The enhanced accessibility of nutrients in the soil was the cause of this increased uptake of N, P, and K. Being a leguminous crop, cowpeas have the ability to fix nitrogen, which has led to the soil being more nutrient-rich. Because nitrogen, phosphorous, and potassium work in concert, raising nitrogen levels may have also raised the concentrations of P and K in cowpea plants, leading to an increase in their absorption. The current results are consistent with those of Ruheentaj et al. (2020).

Effect of INM practices on Microbial Population of Soil

Highest soil microbial population viz: bacterial, fungus and actinomycetes was recorded with T₈(STD₇₅ + BFs + VC) among all the treatments. Highest bacterial, fungus and actinomycetes population of 49.40(x 10⁶cfu g⁻¹ of soil), 22.63 (x 10⁵cfu g⁻¹ of soil) and 30.93 (x 10⁴cfu g⁻¹ of soil) were recorded with treatment T₈ followed by T₇. Lowest microbial population was recorded with control. It was found that when organics were incorporated with inorganic the microbial population increase in the soil as they get better environment for their activity as depicted in Fig. 3. This result was in conformity with Chellemi *et al.* (2008) and SonaJavorekova *et al.* (2015). Proteins, organic acids, and antioxidants are secreted by the microbial strength found in organics or biofertilizers to convert soil organic materials into energy that promotes the growth of beneficial microorganisms in the rhizosphere. (2014) Devakumar *et al.* After applying organics and biofertilizers, the soil microbial population may become more abundant due to a favorable rhizospheric microenvironment created by root exudates, soil aggregation, the breakdown of organic matter and root cells, the availability of plant nutrients, and other physical-biochemical processes. The findings were consistent with those of Sona Javorekova *et al.* (2015), Rudra Pratap *et al.* (2024), and Chellemietal (2008).

Effect of INM practices on Economics of cowpea cultivation

The different INM practices influenced the cost of cultivation which varied in the range of Rs 40,500 and Rs 56,200, lowest with control and highest with STD₁₀₀+BFs+VC. The gross return varied between Rs 87,396 and Rs 2,05,400, lowest with control and highest with STD₇₅+BFs+VC. The net return from different packages ranged from Rs 46,896 to Rs 1,51,400, lowest with control and highest with STD₇₅+BFs+VC. The rise in gross income, net income, and B:C ratio may be owing to increased production due to increased nutrition availability with combined application of nutrient sources as shown in Fig.4. The present finding is in agreement with the findings of Patel and Thanki (2020).

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Compliance with ethical standards

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest

Ethical issues: "None"

Figure 1. Effect of INM practices on growth parameters of Cowpea crop

Figure 2. Effect of INM practices on nutrient uptake of Cowpea crop

Figure 3. Effect of INM practices on microbial population of cowpea cultivation

Figure 4. Effect of INM practices on economics of cowpea cultivation

Table 1. Details of treatments are given below

SI No	Treatment	Treatment Description	Abbreviation
1	T ₁	Absolute Control	Control
2	T ₂	Farmers Practice (N-P ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ O ha ⁻¹ @ 15-30-20 kg)	FP
3	T ₃	Soil Test Dose (N-P ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ O ha ⁻¹ @ 25-50-40 kg)	STD
4	T ₄	100% Soil Test Dose + Seed treatment with <i>Rhizobium</i> biofertilizer @ 20g/kg of seed + PSM @ 4kg/ha	STD ₁₀₀ + BF _s
5	T ₅	75% Soil Test Dose + Seed treatment with <i>Rhizobium</i> biofertilizer @ 20g/kg of seed + PSM @ 4kg/ha + FYM @ 5t/ha	STD ₇₅ + BF _s + F
6	T ₆	100% Soil Test Dose + Seed treatment with <i>Rhizobium</i> biofertilizer @ 20g/kg of seed + PSM @ 4kg/ha + FYM @ 5t/ha	STD ₁₀₀ + BF _s + F
7	T ₇	75% Soil Test Dose + Seed treatment with <i>Rhizobium</i> biofertilizer @ 20g/kg of seed + PSM @ 4kg/ha + VC	STD ₇₅ + BF _s + VC

		Vermicompost @ 2.5t/ha	
8	T ₈	100% Soil Test Dose + Seed treatment with <i>Rhizobium</i> biofertilizer @ 20g/kg of seed + PSM @ 4kg/ha + Vermicompost @ 2.5t/ha	STD ₁₀₀ + BFs +VC

Table 2. Effect of INM practices on yield of Cowpea crop

Sl. No.	Treatments	Yield (fresh)	Dry matter			Harvest Index	RAE*	
			(t ha ⁻¹)				(%)	
			Pod	Stover	Total		(a)	(b)
1	T ₁	7.28	1.99	3.33	5.32	37.4	-	-
2	T ₂	8.05 (10.5)*	2.48 (24.6)*	3.77 (13.2)*	6.25 (17.5)*	39.7	36	36
3	T ₃	8.31 (14.1)	2.55 (28.1)*	4.13 (24.0)*	6.68 (25.6)*	38.2	49	53
4	T ₄	8.77 (20.4)	2.69 (5.5)**	4.27 (3.4)**	6.96 (7.14)**	38.7	70	63
5	T ₅	9.05 (24.2)	3.56 (39.6)**	4.57 (10.7)**	8.13 (21.7)**	43.7	83	108
6	T ₆	9.41 (29.2)	3.44 (34.9)**	4.45 (7.7)**	7.89 (18.1)**	43.6	100	100
7	T ₇	10.27 (41.0)	3.73 (46.3)**	4.72 (14.3)**	8.45 (26.5)**	44.1	141	120
8	T ₈	9.80 (34.6)	3.58 (40.4)**	4.59 (11.1)**	8.17 (22.3)**	43.8	119	110
SEm(±)		0.789	0.027	0.108	0.098	-	-	-
CD (P=0.05)		2.392	0.081	0.327	0.297	-	-	-

RAE calculated considering the economic yield due to STD + BFs + F as 100.

- (a) RAE based on economic yield.
- (b) RAE based on biomass yield.

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